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АКАДЕМИЯСИ МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН
АКАДЕМИЯСИ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

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МУНДАРИЖА

ИҚТИСОДИЁТ ФАНЛАР

Абдуллаев У.А. Информационная поисковая система и математическая модель задач мониторинга предприятий торговли	4
Ахмедова Н.Ш. Особенности стратегии развития интеграции малых и крупных строительных предприятий	10
Баймирзаев Д.Н. Агросаноат мажмуасида нархлар диспаратети муаммосини тартибга солиш йўналишлари	15
Исмаилов Д.А., Аманов А.Р. Инвестиция фаолиятини молиявий бошқариш механизмини такомиллаштириш йўналишлари	20
Мадаминов И.О. Инновацион иқтисодий ўсишга ўтиш давр талаби	26
Рахимова М. Минтақани комплекс ривожлантиришда экологик мухитнинг ўрни ...	33

ТАРИХ ФАНЛАРИ

Баратов С.Р. Знаки и надписи на керамических изделиях из поселения Хумбузтепа	37
Воҳидова К.А. Исҳоқхон тўра Ибратнинг “Тарихи маданият” асари ҳақида	47
Насретдинова Д.М. Туркистонда хотин-қизлар маорифини ташкил этишда татар аёллари	50
Очиллов А.Т. Бухоронинг қадимги давр тарихини ёритишда Яхё Ғуломов археологик тадқиқотларининг ўрни	51

ФИЛОЛОГИЯ ФАНЛАРИ

Akhmedov R.Sh. The unity of theme and structure in isaac asimov’s foundation series	54
Isomiddinova L.I. Modern educational technologies in teaching English	56
Niyazmetova Sh.K. Phraseological units with onomastic, its origin and translation:ways..	58
Абдуллаева Б. Шеърини баёнда топишмоқларнинг иштироки	62
Имамова З.Т. Современные методы в преподавании французского языка	65
Юлдашев Д. Т. Алишер Навоий асарларидаги айрим антропонимлар антропоцентрик талқини	67

ПЕДАГОГИКА ФАНЛАРИ

Begliyev S.B., Jumaniyozova T.M. Biologiya fanidan kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishda pisa xalqaro tadqiqot dasturidagi testlarning ahamiyati	69
Matyakubova Yu.A. “O’simliklarning changlanishi” mavzusini o’qitishda FSMU texnologiyasining afzalligi	72
Matyakubova Yu.A., Yusupova S.Q. Genetika fanidan o’simliklarda modda va energiya almashinuviga oid murakkab masalalarning yechish uslublari	74
Salayeva N., Xudayberganova Sh., Begliyev R. O`quvchilarga individual yondoshishning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari	77

ТИББИЁТ ФАНЛАРИ

Дусчанов Б.А., Рахимов Б.М. Куйдаво	81
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ФИЛОЛОГИЯ ФАНЛАРИ

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THE UNITY OF THEME AND STRUCTURE IN ISAAC ASIMOV'S FOUNDATION SERIES

R.Sh.Akhmedov, a senior teacher, Gulistan State University, Gulistan

Аннотация: Адабиётшунослик фани учун Айзек Азимовнинг “Ташкилот” асарини ўрганиш муҳим аҳамият касб этади. Ушбу асар нафақат жанрни ўзига хослиги ва ижтимоий фалсафий қарашлари билан, балки ўзининг мурракаб тузилиши билан ҳам ажралиб туради. Айзек Азимов ўзининг асосий гоясини фақат шакл ва мавзунинг бирлиги орқали етказишига эришди.

Калим сўзлар: илмий фантастика, Азимов, “Ташкилот” трилогияси, мавзу, тузилиши.

Аннотация: Изучение серии «Основание» Айзека Азимова представляет собой огромный интерес для литературоведческой науки. Кроме жанрового своеобразие и социально-философской направленности научно-фантастических сюжетов, серия отличается сложной структурой. Только через неразрывность структуры и тематики Азимов смог передать главную идею произведения.

Ключевые слова: научная фантастика, Азимов, трилогия «Основание», тема, структура.

Abstract: The study of Isaac Asimov's Foundation series presents a great interest for literary science. Except some genre peculiarities and socio-philosophical orientation of SF plots, the Series differs by its complex structure. Only through the unity of structure and theme Asimov could transmit the main idea of the work.

Key words: science fiction, Asimov, Foundation trilogy, theme, structure.

Introduction. Isaac Asimov (January 2, 1920 - April 6, 1992) - American science fiction writer, popularizer of science, a biochemist, the author of about 500 books (primarily in science fiction genre, but also in other genres, such as fantasy, detective, humor), the winner of Hugo and Nebula Awards. Some terms from his fiction, such as “robotics”, “positronic”, “psychohistory” - have become firmly established in English and other languages. According to English-American literary tradition, Isaac Asimov, along with Arthur Clarke and Robert Heinlein, belongs to the so-called “Big Three” of science fiction writers.

The Foundation inspired authors from Douglas Adams to George Lucas, and public figures such as Paul Krugman and Newt Gingrich. In 1966, the original trilogy won the Hugo Award as the best science fiction of all time, beating the Lord of the Rings. Isaac Asimov himself later admitted that he did not expect to win, because he believed that Tolkien would win. This achievement becomes even more remarkable if we consider that the story in the series - the epic story about the fall and ascent of the future galactic empires - contains almost no trail inherent in science fiction. Novels cover the whole galaxy, but there are no habitual aliens there. It also shows the future history of human society, but it can be called neither utopia no dystopia. There are many futuristic technologies present, but they all serve only as a background, but not as a driving force or a plot basis. In fact, the entire book contradicts Isaac Asimov's own definition of science fiction as “a branch of literature dealing with people's reactions to changes in science and technology.” [1]

Although Isaac Asimov later explained that he decided to establish a genre called social science fiction. He used the future as a template to explore the basic idea, which people have been thinking about for a long time: “Are the laws of human history as unbreakable as the laws of physics?”

Foundation trilogy (“The Foundation”, “The Foundation and the Empire,” and “The Second Foundation”) was not created as a single work: there were the combined stories that the writer wrote between 1941 and 1950. The stories are linked chronologically, but separated from each other by decades, and for the most part, each of them has a different set of characters. The basic idea is the idea of psychohistory – an attempt of a relatively small Foundation to survive against a stronger enemy, and it can do this only by recognizing and working with historical forces associated with the situation. Creating a “psychohistory” was conceived as a merger of the physical and social sciences. As Isaac Asimov explains: “I would like to consider essentially psychohistory as a science invented by me. It was, in a sense, a struggle between free will and determinism. On the other hand, I would like to make a story similar to the “Decline and Fall of the Roman Empire”, but on a much larger scale, a whole galaxy. To do this, I took the aura of the Roman Empire and described it exaggeratedly. The social system is very similar to the Roman imperial system, but for me it was just a skeleton.” [1]

The so-called “Seldon Crisis” in the trilogy has two forms: 1) events unfold in such a way that there is only one way to follow, 2) The forces of history conspired to determine the result. But the general thing is that one's desire does not matter. Protagonists and antagonists believe that their decisions will matter when,

in fact, the future is already predetermined. One of the most common criticisms that have been raised in the Foundation trilogy is Isaac Asimov's premise that human behavior never changes. At the time of publication of the trilogy, science fiction writers had already adhered to the idea that with advances in science and technology, human nature would change. This idea has intensified with the advent of transhumanism - the concept that people will eventually use technological and biological means to change the course of their own evolution. "How could psychohistory predict the behavior of the masses when its participants were no longer full-fledged people? The idea is that humanity as a whole is unable to change and, therefore, does not have free will. The only solution is a good ruling class that can save us from ourselves." [2]

In the preface to the special edition of the 2012 Foundation, the Nobel Prize winner, economist Paul Krugman writes: "What it means for the narrative is that the structure of the conflict should not be built like a normal story about heroes and villains, and in the novels there should be a bit of cynicism." [4]

Chronologically, the story's ending is so complicated that the author left more than 500 years ago only to find a lighter topic for his last two books of the series, leaving the readers wondering in which direction the author could move on. And it is this understatement, despite the external complexity, that makes the story so interesting, leaving the reader to think about whether it is possible for the world to exist after the main plot of the books of the cycle, a world that psychohistory could not have foreseen, and therefore changed. The creation of an ideal universe has always been a pressing issue of our time and, for not having magic, these same "creators" turned to science. But the human factor has always reserved the right of the last choice, unlike machines, even very intelligent machines.

Discussion. The only aspect investigated in most scientific researches concerning Isaac Asimov's Foundation trilogy is the problem of robotics and psychohistory. Of course, these concepts are worth to be analyzed and made the writer one of the most popular and distinguished authors of science fiction. Unfortunately, literary critics separate the ideas and various explanations of the writer, discussed in the trilogy, and, as a result, do not reveal general panorama. The minority of the researchers, such as James Gunn and Jean Fiedler, in some way touched the problem of the structural and thematic unity of the novels included into the Foundation series. [3]

In fact, in science fiction there is a great number of novels characterized by their specific structure and single major theme. They are constructed, like Foundation trilogy, from a number of smaller stories and form so-called "composite novel". The proportion of composite novels in the genre of science fiction in the USA is rather high. Several reasons, both practical and philosophical, account for this phenomenon. For those writers who achieved prominence during and immediately after the "Golden Age," novel-length publication in the predominantly hardcover market was simply impossible. They confined themselves to short stories, or at least highly episodic narratives, for the science fiction magazines. When book-length publication later became a reality, the first move for many writers was to collect several short stories, perhaps with minor changes, to form a more or less coherent narrative. Isaac Asimov's "I, Robot" story collection and Ray Bradbury's "Martian Chronicles" can be named among such narratives masquerading as novels manqué, to name just a few.

Isaac Asimov's novels of the Foundation Series have a singular major plot. The Series are composed of many novels, each being an important part of the central idea of the work. The structure of the Series helps the readers to follow this idea smoothly and easily. According to the great interrelationship in the plot, the sections of the Foundation fit together comfortably and form a unified whole.

The Foundation series were originally a series of eight short stories published between 1942 and 1950. According to Isaac Asimov, the idea of writing the trilogy appeared when he was reading Edward Gibbon's "History of the Decline and Fall of the Roman Empire". [3] The first four stories were united in the novel titled simply as "Foundation". Other stories were published in pairs under the titles "Foundation and Empire" and "Second Foundation". These three novels are known as Foundation trilogy. After the Foundation series had long been considered the most important work of modern science fiction, Isaac Asimov was convinced by his publishers and readers to write next novel "Foundation's Edge". He followed this with a sequel novel, "Foundation and Earth" (1983), and five years later – with prequel novels under the titles "Prelude to Foundation" and "Forward the Foundation". During the lapse between sequels and prequels, Isaac Asimov connected his Foundation series to his various other series, creating a single unified universe. Creation of his or her own Universe has always been an ample evidence of writer's literary skills. The Universe of Isaac Asimov was submitted and highly assessed by many literary critics.

The series is set in the same universe as Isaac Asimov's first published novel, "The Pebble in the Sky", although Foundation takes place approximately ten thousand years later. "The Pebble in the Sky"

became the basis for the Empire Series. Then, at some unknown date (prior to writing “The Foundation's Edge”) Isaac Asimov decided to merge the Foundation/Empire series with his Robot series. Thus, all three series are set in the same universe, giving them a combined length of 15 novels. The merge also created a time-span of the series of approximately 20.000 years. [5]

Thus, the Foundation Series can be considered as an epic science fiction series. It consists of seven volumes that are closely linked to each other, although they can be read separately. In total, there are fifteen novels and dozens of short stories written by Isaac Asimov, and six novels written by other authors after his death, expanding the time spanned by more than twenty thousand years. The series is highly acclaimed, winning the one-time Hugo Award for “Best All-Time Series” in 1966.

More accurately, the plot of the series focuses on the growth and reach of the Foundation, against a backdrop of the “decline and fall of the Galactic Empire”. The first main character of the series is Hari Seldon who spent his life developing a branch of mathematics known as psychohistory, a concept devised by Isaac Asimov. Using the law of mass action, it can predict the future, but only on a large scale; it is error-prone on a small scale. It works on the principle that the behavior of a mass of people is predictable if the quantity of this mass is very large (equal to the population of the galaxy which has a population of around a quadrillion). The larger the mass, the more predictable is the future.

Conclusion. In many ways, the Foundation series is unique as a science fiction novel. The focus of the books is certainly the trends through which a civilization might progress, specifically seeking to analyze their progress, using history as a precedent. Although many science fiction novels such as “The Nineteen Eighty-Four or Fahrenheit 451” do this, their focus is upon how current trends in society might come to fruition, and act as a moral allegory on the modern world. The Foundation series, on the other hand, looks at the trends in a wider scope, not necessarily looking at what the societies change into, but how they change and adapt. It is one of the main reasons why Foundation should always be investigated as an undividable whole.

The ideas are developed step by step and totally changed from one novel to another. If any specialist begins to investigate the first novel of the series separately, he will soon be sure that Isaac Asimov supports the ideas of monarchy and middle age traditions. It is, of course, absolutely wrong. Isaac Asimov, trying to cover all stages of humanity’s development, just depicts the first one in his first novel. The second stage is shown accurately in the second novel, and so on. Furthermore, the concept of psychohistory gives the events in the story a sense of dualism. Hari Seldon himself hopes that his Plan will “reduce 30,000 years of Dark Ages and barbarism to a single millennium.” [5] And this idea can be found by some researcher and reader only after having read the last lines of the Foundation series.

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MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

L.I. Isomiddinova, senior lecturer, Tashkent state technical University, Tashkent

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o’qitishda zamonaviy ta’lim texnologiyalari va uning ta’lim samaradorligiga ta’siri yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so’zlar: ta’lim, ta’lim metodlari, zamonaviy ta’lim, ingliz tili, pedagogik texnologiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещены современные образовательные технологии в преподавании английского языка и его влияние на образовательную эффективность.

Ключевые слова: образования, методы обучения, современное образование, английский язык, педагогическая технология.

Abstract: This article highlights modern educational technologies in teaching English and its impact on educational effectiveness.

Key words education, teaching methods, modern education, English, pedagogical technology.